

TEACHING ADJECTIVES AND ADVERBS IN ESL CLASSES

Ozlem Yagciogluⁱ

Full-time Instructor,
Dokuz Eylul University,
School of Foreign Languages,
Foreign Languages Department,
Izmir, Turkey

Abstract:

Teaching adjectives and adverbs and adverbs is a very important subject in English language education. If the students who learn English as a second or a third language can use adjectives and adverbs effectively, they can be more successful in understanding the articles they read. They can also be more successful in business life. Because people can speak English effectively and fluently can find better jobs. This study deals with teaching adjectives and adverbs in the classes where English is taught as a second or as a third language. Definitions of the word 'adjective' and the word 'adverb' will be given. The role of the adjectives and adverbs will be highlighted. Sample classroom activities will be shared.

Keywords: Adjectives and Adverbs; ESL Classes; Sample Classroom Activities

1. Introduction

Adjectives and adverbs are the important parts of the sentences. They give different meanings to the sentences we use. They should be used correctly. Otherwise, the meanings of the sentences can be misunderstood. In our modern world, people use many adjectives and adverbs. The ones who can use adjectives and adverbs in English correctly are efficient in communication. Teaching these subjects in the classes where English is taught as a second or as a foreign language is important for the students who would like to learn English effectively and speak fluently. This study will help colleagues to teach adjectives and adverbs joyfully.

ⁱ Correspondence: email ozlemygcgl@gmail.com

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 What is Adjective?

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, adjective is defined as:

"A word that describes a noun or pronoun:

"Big", "boring", "purple", and "obvious" are all adjectives. "

(<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/adjective>)

It has been defined on the Merriam-Webster Dictionary as:

"A word belonging to one of the major form classes in any of numerous languages and typically serving as a modifier of a noun to denote a quality of the thing named, to indicate its quantity or extent, or to specify a thing as distinct from something else. //

The word red in "the red car" is an adjective."

(<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/adjective>)

2.2 What is Adverb?

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, adverb has been defined as:

"Adverbs are one of the four major word classes, along with nouns, verbs and adjectives. We use adverbs to add more information about a verb, an adjective, another adverb, a clause or a whole sentence and, less commonly, about a noun phrase."

(<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/grammar/british-grammar/about-adjectives-and-adverbs/adverbs>)

Sample sentences for adverbs have been listed by the Cambridge Dictionary as:

"Can you move it carefully? It's fragile.

Quickly! We're late.

She swims really well.

Don't go so fast.

You have to turn it clockwise.

Come over here.

Actually, I don't know her.

I haven't seen them recently.

The bathroom's upstairs on the left."

(<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/grammar/british-grammar/about-adjectives-and-adverbs/adverbs>)

2.3 The Role of English Adjectives in English Language Teaching

Zerkina, Kostina, Urazayeva, Lomakina, Emets, Gallyamova, Melnikova, Trutnev and Lukina (2016:5149) state that;

“Adjectives in English can be represented by two classes: empiric and rational. By the present stage of the English language development there defined several groups of empiric adjectives, that is, the ones “denoting signs perceived by the senses and realized by the person as a result of a single-stage mental comparison operation with “a standard”. Empiric adjectives designate their own signs to specific subjects, their content is in full compliance with the logical and philosophical categories and rational adjectives, that is, indicating the category of signs that are not perceived by the senses, and are the result, comparison, conclusions. It should be noted that adjective attachment to a certain group is quite relative on its main meaning as for its derivative, metaphorical and redefining meaning they can be members of other groups.

Rational adjectives indicate the category of features that are not perceived by the senses and they are the result, comparison, conclusions. Rational adjectives do not form a single class of words, and depending on the compatibility they are divided into four types: adjectives indicating the characteristics of a human, adjectives indicating the signs of animals, adjectives indicating features of objects, adjectives indicating the signs of the animal subjects estimated by a human.”

From the above paragraphs, it can be understood that the adjectives do not represent only one thing. Adjectives which belong to certain groups are mostly related with their main meanings or definitions. Empiric adjectives are related with the specific subjects who have logical and philosophical categories. Rational adjectives are not related with a single class of words. They are the ones for the results, comparison and conclusions.

3. The Purpose of This Study

The primary purpose of this study was to make my students more enjoyable class hours and to make students happier during the course hours. Secondly, it is hoped that this study will help colleagues to teach adjectives and adverbs more joyfully.

4. Objectives of This Study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To help students speak English as much as possible;
2. To remind students the role of the English grammar;
3. To teach adjectives and adverbs effectively.

5. Method

5.1. Participants

The participants consisted of 40 (forty) university students at Dokuz Eylul University in the city of Izmir in Turkey. They were university students in the Prep Classes

Department in the School of Foreign Languages at Dokuz Eylul University in Izmir in Turkey. Their ages ranged from 18-23.

5.2. Teaching Procedure

Different kinds of classroom activities were used according to the interests of the participants. These classroom activities can be listed as follows:

1. Using pictures;
2. Using photographs;
3. Using short video films;
4. Using short documentaries;
5. Using quotes;
6. Using course book exercises;
7. Using grammar questions and sentences;
8. Puzzle games.

A. Sample Classroom Activity 1

Students watched the following short video films twice to learn adjectives and adverbs. They learnt the following words from these videos: fun, easy to get to, breathtaking, encouraging, prosperous, dynamic, inspiring, joyful, and healthy. They also found some other adjectives for Izmir after watching these short films. They repeated all the adjectives they heard loudly.

- My Izmir Movie #Expo2020 #Healthforall: Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fa1ik26EW8Q>
- Expo 2020 My İzmir Movie-2 #Expo2020 #Healthforall. Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eXuxFlmUn10&t=4s>

B. Sample Classroom Activity 2

Students listened to the following song and they were asked to write the adjectives they heard after watching and listening to the following song twice. After all the students gave their answers, all the adjectives were written on the board in the classroom.

- Pharrell Williams - Happy (Official Music Video). Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y6Sxv-sUYtM>

C. Sample Classroom Activity 3

Students were given the definitions of 12 words. These words were written on cards and all of these cards were put on the white board in their classroom. 2 students were invited to walk next to the white board. The definitions of the words were read without saying the words. Students tried to find which definition belongs to the words they were given.

D. Sample Classroom Activity 4

Students were asked to fill in the blanks to repeat the adjectives they learnt. Apart from these questions, I prepared some grammar exercises for them to repeat the adjectives and adverbs.

Adverbs and Adjectives:

Retrieved from:

<https://www.perfect-english-grammar.com/adverbs-or-adjectives-exercise-1.html>

- 1) John held the plate ----- . (careful / carefully)
- 2) Julia is a ----- person. (careful / carefully)
- 3) I ran ----- to the station. (quick / quickly)
- 4) The journey was ----- . (quick / quickly)
- 5) You look ----- . Didn't you sleep well? (tired / tiredly)
- 6) The baby rubbed her eyes ----- . (tired / tiredly)
- 7) She sang ----- . (happy / happily)
- 8) You sound ----- . (happy / happily)
- 9) I speak English ----- . (well / good)
- 10) Her English is ----- . (well / good)
- 11) She cooks ----- . (terrible / terribly)

E. Sample Classroom Activity 5

Students were divided into four groups and each group was given different photos. They were asked to use the adjectives and the adverbs they learnt for the photos they saw.

6. Findings

6.1. Students' Feedback

All of these classroom activities were used in two different classes for the university students in the School of Foreign Languages at Dokuz Eylul University in Izmir in Turkey. Students informed that they enjoyed attending these classroom activities and they improved and developed their speaking skills and their pronunciation.

7. Conclusion

Up to here, the definitions of the word 'adjective' and the word 'adverb' have been given. The role of learning and teaching English adjectives has been highlighted. Sample classroom activities were shared.

Using adjectives and adverbs in English correctly is an important skill in language education and in the world. In the modern world, one of the most important prerequisites is talking correctly. Therefore, university students should know how to use adjectives and adverbs correctly in their sentences.

It is hoped that all colleagues who teach ESL Courses will get benefits of this study and they will create happier class hours.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank all of my students who attended my classes regularly and full-heartedly. I would like to thank all of my colleagues who have given me positive energy and encouraged me to write this paper. I would like to extend special thanks to the readers, to the reviewers, and to the editors of this journal.

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Appendix 1

Websites for Listening, Watching or Reading

- Adjective Order. Retrieved 25 September 2018 from: <https://www.eslvideo.com/quiz.php?id=22065>
- Adverbs and Adjectives. Retrieved 25 September 2018 from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y6Sxv-sUYtM>
- Song for Learning Adjectives. Retrieved 25 September 2018 from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7zMbB3TzuPc&list=PLM57aqHEvHiXGdT2r7wwjQH0w0aQg9quv>

Steven Pinker: What our language habits reveal | TED Talk - TED.com. Retrieved 25 September 2018 from: <https://www.ted.com/talks/.../discussion?...>

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